

A CIRCULAR APPROACH TO HYDROPONICS: UPCYCLED POLYPROPYLENE AND COCONUT FIBER WASTE AS SUSTAINABLE MATERIAL FOR HYDROPONIC GROWTH POTS

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Abstract: *Plant fibres are considered to have great potential for use as reinforcement in the production of value-added recycled plastic composites. Unfortunately, only a small portion of waste plant fibres is utilized as secondary raw materials, while the majority ends up being randomly incinerated or disposed of in landfills. From a materials perspective to achieve sustainable development, the solution lies in moving toward more environmentally friendly trends, which have led to the rise of so-called "biocomposites." Biocomposites are a class of materials formed by blending natural fibres with a matrix material. The natural fibres used in biocomposite production can be derived from various sources, including flax, coconut, hemp, jute, sisal, and bamboo. The matrix material used in biocomposites can vary from biodegradable, non-biodegradable, synthetic to recycled. In this paper, the use of waste polypropylene combined with waste coconut fibres is presented for the production of a low-density pot that enables hydroponic plant cultivation. At the Faculty of Polymer Technology, waste packing belts from the company KO-SI were used in the form of recycled polypropylene, which was ground and mixed with ground waste coconut fibres—an industrial waste product from the company KO-SI. To achieve proper bonding between the matrix and the fibres, a suitable compatibilizer was added. This ensured good interfacial interactions between the waste coconut fibres and the recycled polypropylene matrix. Using computer-aided design (CAD) with Siemens NX 12 software, a 3D model of a pot suitable for hydroponic plant cultivation was first created. This was followed by the construction of a thermoforming tool, which was printed using fused filament fabrication (FFF) technology. With the help of a press, sheets were produced from the prepared composite material. These sheets were then shaped into hydroponic plant pots using a thermoforming machine and the 3D-printed tool.*

Keywords: biocomposites, natural fiber reinforcement, coconut fiber, prototyping

1 INTRODUCTION

Industrial waste is generally better separated from municipal waste and is often much less polluted. This consequently means that additional sorting and washing of industrial waste is not necessary. Recycling of industrial waste is therefore much easier (Ragaert et al., 2017). The main advantage of thermoplastic composites is that the combination of matrix and waste reinforcing fibers produce excellent properties, while at the same time reduce production costs (Zhidan et al., 2011).

Recently, PP recycling has been a very important topic, mainly due to the increasing amount of PP. A large part of the packaging is made of PP. Polypropylene grafted with maleic anhydride as a compatibilizer in the composition of waste coconut fibers and polypropylene matrix allows for better dispersion of waste coconut fibers in the PP matrix. In addition, the use of this compatibilizer improves the interfacial adhesion of waste PP with natural fibers. Waste composite has increased stiffness compared to recycled polypropylene (Zhidan et al., 2011), (Di Bella et al., 2012).

The aim of this study was to ensure sufficient stiffness of the composite material and maintain a sufficiently low density, which in addition to buoyancy, ensures the floating capability of the final product. In addition, the aim was to prepare a functional product from industrial waste materials. As part of the study, it was necessary to design a thermoforming tool and adapt it to the composite material. This is precisely why we chose FFF technology to manufacture these prototype tools. The versions of the thermoforming tool thus differ in geometry to achieve the thermoforming for the simplest production of pots for hydroponics.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the experimental part of the study which was based on previous research on composites reinforced with waste coconut fibers, we prepared two versions of the material with different ratio of additives.

2.1 Sample

In the study, we used industrial waste from the company KO-SI d.o.o. We used coconut fibers from the company KO-SI, which represent industrial waste for which the company is looking for innovative solutions for use and applications in various products. We also received the company's waste packing belts made of polypropylene. For proper bonding, we used the compatibilizer PP-g-MAH (Graftabond 02025A CA). Two versions of the composite material were produced, in the first we used 20 wt.% waste coconut fibers in combination with the addition of 5 wt.% compatibilizer PP-g-MAH (Graftabond 02025A CA) and 75 wt.% rPP. We also produced a version of the material, where we used 30 wt.% waste coconut fibers with the addition of 5 wt.% compatibilizer PP-g-MAH (Graftabond 02025A CA) and 65 wt.% rPP (Table 1).

Table 1: Basic material characteristics of the used invasive plants for packaging

Sample	rPP (wt.%)	Coconut fiber (wt.%)	PP-g-MAH (wt.%)
0	100	/	/
1	75	20	5
2	65	30	5

Before compounding, the coconut waste fibers were grinded and than dried to a moisture content below 0.1 wt.%. After compounding, the biocomposite was also dried to a moisture content below 0.1 wt.%. All samples were first compounded on a Labtech LTE 20-44 twin-screw extruder. The screw diameter was 20 mm, the L/D ratio was 44:1, the screw speed was 300 min⁻¹, and the barrel temperature ranged from 165 °C at the inlet to 190 °C at the nozzle. The nozzle had two 4 mm diameter openings. The filaments were fed through a water bath (15 °C) into a Scheer granulator, where the filaments were cut to a length of about 5 mm. All three samples were extruded and granulated into pellets.

Using a press, we produced sheets for thermoforming. The samples were prepared with a Baopin BP-8170-B press. Before thermoforming, the material was evenly distributed between the metal plates. The composite material was then inserted into the heated press with the plates. The temperature of the upper and lower heating plates of the press was 185 °C. First, a profile with a lower pre-pressing pressure of 0.25 MPa was used, which lasted 90 s. The pressure was then increased to 2 MPa for 60 s. This was followed by cooling the heating plates to a plate temperature of 60 °C, after which the press

opened. The composite sheet was then left between two metal plates until it cooled. Figure 1 shows the used materials and the produced products.

Figure 1: PP packing belts (top left), waste coconut fiber (top middle), biocomposite granulate with 20 wt.% waste coconut fiber (top right), samples cut from the sheet used for laboratory tests (bottom left) and composite sheet (bottom right)

2.2 Laboratory tests

The tensile test was performed on a Shimadzu AG-X plus 10 kN tensile testing machine. This was performed in accordance with ISO 527. The distance between the clamping assembly was 115 mm, the testing speed to 0.25 % elongation was 1 mm/min, and above 0.25 % was 50 mm/min.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed on a Perkin Elmer TGA 4000 instrument. The sample was heated from 40 °C to 550 °C, with a heating rate of 10 °C/min, in a nitrogen atmosphere (20 mL/min), and then held isothermally at 550 °C for 5 min in an oxygen atmosphere (20 mL/min).

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was performed on a Mettler Toledo DSC 2 calorimeter according to ISO 11357. The heating and cooling rate was 10 °C/min. The samples were heated from -50 °C to 200 °C, followed by an isothermal segment at 200 °C for 5 min. They were then cooled from 200 °C to -50 °C, followed by an isothermal segment at -50 °C for 5 min. Then all steps were repeated once more.

2.3 Procedure of making pots for hydroponics

We used Siemens NX 12 CAD program to model the pot and the tool. First, we drew a 3D model of a pot suitable for growing plants with hydroponics. This was followed by the construction of a thermoforming tool based on the pot. Different versions of the tool were also prepared. These versions of the thermoforming tools were printed using FFF 3D printing technology, using polyethylene terephthalate glycol (PETG) manufactured by Plastika Trček. For 3D printing, we used a Tumaaker Bigfoot 500 Pro Dual 3D printer. Thermoforming was done with FormBox FBA 180123EU. Prepared composite sheets were clamped into the thermoforming machine and heated up. The thermoforming tool was then inserted into the thermoforming machine. With the assistance of vacuum, sheets were thermoformed into pots. Based on the thermoforming results the optimal tool and optimal material version were used to produce a larger quantity of hydroponic pots. We could not produce pots with material sample 2, due to the higher content of coconut fibers that resulted in processing issues because of the brittleness of produced sheets. Therefore, measurements were made only on samples 0 and 1.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Laboratory tests were performed on a version of the material that proved to be more suitable for thermoforming (sample 1). The use of waste coconut fibers in combination with a compatibilizer in the rPP matrix in sample 1 increases the tensile E modulus (E). From Figure 2, the tensile strength (σ_m) is slightly reduced compared to the tensile strength of rPP (sample 0). The elongation at tensile strength (ϵ_m) and the elongation at break (ϵ_b) are significantly reduced (Figure 3).

Figure 2: Tensile E-modulus and tensile strength (left figure) and elongation at tensile strength and elongation at break (right figure)

As a result of good interfacial interactions between waste coconut fibers and rPP due to the compatibilizer PP-g-MA, we can observe an increase in tensile stiffness by 68 wt.%. We can also observe a decrease in tensile strength by 6 wt.%, which can be concluded that this occurs because the length of coconut fibers is smaller than the critical length of coconut fibers. We can also observe that the standard deviation of the tensile strength of sample 1 increases to the extent that it is in the range of the tensile strength of sample 0. We can conclude that PP-g-MA is a good compatibilizer, since the tensile stiffness increases significantly, but due to the smaller length of coconut fibers, a slightly lower tensile strength can be observed.

TGA analysis shows a one-step decomposition of the sample. From Table 2, we can see that the composite with added waste coconut fibers undergoes a two-step decomposition. The first decomposition at a lower temperature is the decomposition of the coconut fibers in composite, the second at a higher temperature is the decomposition of the rPP matrix with additives, compared to sample 0 we can see that sample 1 has a higher degradation temperature of matrix, which may be a result of a higher degree of crystallinity due to the addition of coconut fibers. We can also observe 6.8 wt.% inorganic fillers, which are a result of mineral substances in natural fibers (Table 2).

Table 2: TGA analysis results

Sample	T_{d1} (°C)	T_{d2} (°C)	Residue (wt.%)
0	/	437.7	0.00
1	337.8	464.4	6.83

The addition of waste coconut fibers does not affect the melting point of the rPP biocomposite. The glass transition is at -11.9 °C, the melting point is at 166 °C. From Table 3, the glass transition temperature is slightly reduced due to the added coconut fibers, which act as nucleation agent and enable a higher degree of crystallinity to be achieved.

Table 3: DSC analysis results

Sample	T_g (°C)	T_c (°C)	ΔH_c (J/g)	T_m (°C)	ΔH_m (J/g)	X_c (%)
0	-3.9	123.8	58.46	165.7	64.33	31
1	-11.9	125.4	49.09	166.0	55.60	38

In Figure 4, we can see a cross-section of the pot model based on this geometry.

Figure 4: Cross-section of the crucible model

In the model of the pot itself, we considered the direction of thermoforming, we also tried to avoid sudden changes in the geometry in the thermoforming direction of the composite sheet. That is why on the model we can see an angle of 110° and a radius of 7 mm in the inner part of the pot. Based on this geometry of the pot the first version of the thermoforming tool was modeled (Figure 5). First a male version of the tool was modeled to produce a greater thickness in the middle of the product. For the usage of vacuum during thermoforming small holes with a diameter of 1 mm in the direction of transformation were implemented.

Figure 5: Male version of the cup thermoforming tool

Because of the localized sagging during heating we decided to model a second female version of the tool. We also considered the less efficient vacuum application from the first version. For this reason, holes with initial diameter of 2 mm were made. The diameter was then reduced to 1 mm in the last 3 mm of the hole length. To produce this part easier with printing, a 3 mm chamfer was used in the transition of the hole from 2 mm to 1 mm (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Male version of the cup thermoforming tool

It turned out that the change in shape had a significant impact on the quality of the pots produced. The final female version of the tool can be seen in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Female version of the cup thermoforming tool

4 CONCLUSIONS

As part of the research, we tested a biocomposite prepared from rPP, waste coconut fibers and with the addition of the compatibilizer PP-g-MA. The stiffness of the biocomposite with waste coconut fibers and PP-g-MA is significantly higher compared to rPP. The strength of the biocomposite with waste coconut fibers and PP-g-MA is slightly lower compared to rPP, this could be due to the length of the used coconut fibers, which might be shorter than the critical length of coconut fibers. The higher stiffness and slightly lower strength confirm good interactions between the components of the biocomposite due to the compatibilizer PP-g-MA. The thermal stability of biocomposite with waste coconut fibers is higher compared to rPP. The melting point and crystallization temperature of biocomposites with waste coconut fibers do not change compared to rPP. The degree of crystallinity of biocomposites is higher compared to rPP. The glass transition temperature is in the case of biocomposite shifts to a slightly lower temperature, which is because of higher degree of crystallinity of the biocomposite. The higher degree of crystallinity occurs due to coconut fibers in the matrix, which act as nucleating agents. This also improved mechanical and thermal properties of the biocomposite.

As part of the research, we also developed the optimal shape of the pot and, based on the product and properties of the composite material, the shape of the tool. This shape enables easier production of pots for growing plants with hydroponics. In addition, we managed to prepare a material from waste materials with the help of an appropriate compatibilizer that can be transformed into a functional product. As part of the study, we also demonstrated the use of FFF technology for the rapid production of prototype tools (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Male version of the tool (top right), female version of the tool (top left), and pot for growing plants with hydroponics (bottom middle)

5 REFERENCES

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